

LUNG TUMOR DETECTION USING DEEP CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract

In simple terms, lung cancer is a significant challenge that the fields of science and medicine are working hard to overcome, which gives the highest mortality rate, besides being one of the smallest survival rates after diagnosis. Thereby, early detection is essential for diagnosis and treatment. All people in this universe require a proper diagnosis of the tumor. Diagnosis need to be in maximizing the payoff. Increasing the payoff is much important mainly in medical diagnosis. Machines need to do an intelligent task in diagnosis of tumor and in this case the lung tumor. Here, the investigation is done with different solvers. Deep learning with a Convolutional Neural Network compatible with the analysis of Computer tomography scans with tumors; the level of accuracy in predictions sees a tremendous enhancement. Classification of tumors by Convolutional Neural Network as malignant or benign with good accuracy is obtained.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Network, Deep Learning, Solver, Artificial Neural Network, Can Net, OTSU Thresholding.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the earlier days, people enjoyed longer lifespans and were largely unaffected by the occurrence of tumors, a term seldom heard by both individuals and medical professionals. However, as the 20th century emerged, tumors became a frequent topic of discussion among humans and physicians alike, as they began to affect people of all ages and manifest in various regions of the body, including the brain. Brain tumors, whether malignant or benign in nature, present a diverse range of types and are typically categorized into two main classifications. Recognizable symptoms of a brain tumor encompass [1] headaches, confusion, and seizures, among others. Lung cancer is seen commonly in males nowadays. Women get affected by breast cancer as well as lung cancer. Women are dying more due to lung cancer compared to breast cancer. Lung cancer is an uncontrolled spreading of cells. Lung cancer occurs in different regions in the human lungs. Mostly it occurs in epithelial cells of bronchi and bronchioles. Mostly lung cancer arises due to the use of cigarette smoking. Based on the number of cigarettes smoked by a person the risk of getting lung cancer increases. Usage of tobacco, which causes lung cancer, has 4000 chemical components, which are cancer-causing ones.

Also known as carcinogens. Tobacco contains Nitrosamines and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, which are the primary cause of carcinogens. Uranium decay produces by-products like radon, which causes cancer. Around 15,000-22,000 lung cancer are due to this radon gas. Pollutants may also raise the effect of cancer. Mainly air pollution gives rise to the development of lung cancer. Individuals who are affected with lung cancer and inhale the polluted air may die. The percentage of death based on this is 1%. Lung cancer is also known as bronchogenic carcinomas because the cancer is formed in the bronchus, which is in the lung. Cancer, which is formed in the lungs, can be of two types:

- 1) Small Cell Lung Cancer (SCLC) and
- 2) Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC), depending on the microscopic appearance of the tumor cells.

SCLC and NSCLC develop differently in human lungs. Treatment for these two types of lung cancer is also different. So it is essential to distinguish between these two types. Among all lung cancers, SCLC occurs in about 20% of humans having cancer. It grows rapidly. SCLC is mainly due to cigarette smoking. But one can say maybe 1% of SCLC tumors occur in non-smokers. Small Cell Lung Cancer rapidly spreads in many places within the body. Under the microscope, the SCLC-type cells appear like oats and so the term is called oats cell cancer. 80 % of cancer is normally NSCLC Normally it was found after causing serious spread i n the person. Based on the type of cell this can again classify into 3 types. Aden carcinoma is a type of cancer seen in the U.S, which is NSCLC. Around 50% of NSCLC found in humans are Aden carcinomas.

In [4] the input lung image was taken from chest radiographs. Input images are down-sampled to 512×512 pixels. After that, the image is converted to grayscale to avoid RGB input image. For that image, contrast enhancement is applied. For that, segmentation is applied by using a shadow filter to enhance the lung image outlines. Then local thresholding is applied by using multilevel thresholding to remove unwanted regions. Dilation is a fundamental operation [3] in image processing that enlarges objects within a binary image, while edge refinement techniques are employed to eliminate noise and enhance the quality of edges. In [7] the input image is taken from a chest X-ray. Preprocessing refers to the initial stage of image enhancement, where efforts are made to improve the quality of the input image. One of the techniques employed during preprocessing involves the use of a median filter, which effectively eliminates noise from the input image, resulting in a cleaner and more refined visual representation. By employing the Gabor filter, a set of essential features, such as Mean, Variance, Standard Deviation, Contrast, Correlation, Homogeneity, and Energy, will be extracted from the input data. These features play a crucial role in characterizing the visual information and can be utilized for various tasks, such as image analysis, pattern recognition, and computer vision applications. Two steps followed here are Image enhancement and Image filtering. It is used to remove irrelevant data, noise and to enhance the image. For that enhanced image, segmentation is applied to detect the lung boundaries by intensity method [5] and discontinuity method (edge detection). Artificial neural networks are employed for the classification of lung diseases, where they process local data from the affected area and establish communication with other network elements. Through this

approach, the neural network effectively categorizes lung diseases based on patterns and characteristics present in the input data, enabling accurate diagnosis and potential treatment recommendations. Finally, the input lung image is classified. In [2] the input image is taken from MRI.

The preprocessing technique used is histogram equalization in which histogram is obtained as the number of pixels having the corresponding gray level. Then the image enhancement is done by Gabor filter. Image feature extraction is used to estimate the size of the tumor. In [8] the input image is taken from CT. In order to eliminate redundancy from scanned images without compromising their features, image-preprocessing techniques like thresholding and histogram equalization are applied. Subsequently, these enhanced images undergo feature extraction, allowing the detection and isolation of specific desired portions or shapes within the image. For that image, segmentation is applied by using the K means algorithm and PSO method. In [9] the input image taken for investigation purpose is a CT image. For that pre-processed lung image enhancement is performed. There are two types of enhancement techniques namely spatial domain and frequency domain. And classified using SVM as benign or malignant in [1] the input image is taken from CT lung images. Image preprocessing, region of interest, segmentation, [2] feature extractions are done. Based on this detection of lung cancer using Back-propagation has been implemented.

The preprocessing is applied to remove noise using a median filter. This requires improvement in the image. Adaptive histogram equalization is employed to enhance the contrast of the image, effectively improving its visual quality and making it more suitable for various image-processing tasks. The intensity value subsequently got improved. This image is further used for obtaining the GLCM matrix, which gives the features: Then ANN classifier is used to classify the image is cancer or noncancerous. In [6] the lung image can be taken from CT medical modalities. Preprocessing technique can be applied to reduce the computational complexity and the median filter is used to remove the salt and pepper noise. Finally, the segmentation has been done by watershed. In [3] Lung cancer became the hectic one nowadays. Doctors are facing difficulty in treating due to its high occurrences in recent years. One of the statistics says lung cancer occurred in human being is the greatest among all diseases encountered by people. Timeley detection of cancer is very much essential for successful cancer treatment. In [3] two methods of segmentation are preferred for cancer detection from images. OTSU thresholding and Watershed transformation are the two different techniques used to find the cancer cell from gray-level Computed Tomography (CT) images. [3] CT images are the datasets obtained from various cancer hospitals, which comprises of images of different patients. In [5], the extraction of lung tissues involves the utilization of lung computed tomography (CT) images sourced from the Lung Image Database Consortium-Image Database Resource Initiative (LIDC-IDRI) database, which serves as the primary data repository for lung imaging studies.

The primary phase of the research paper involves two distinct stages, namely preprocessing and segmentation. The first stage, preprocessing, encompasses essential steps aimed at enhancing the quality of the lung CT images. Initially, noise removal is

conducted using a Wiener filter, which effectively reduces unwanted artifacts and disturbances present in the images. Subsequently, contrast enhancement techniques are employed; specifically utilizing contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE). This approach ensures that the contrast levels in the images are optimized, leading to improved visualization and enhanced details of the lung tissues. In the second stage, segmentation using OTSU thresholding is carried out to extract the lung tissues.

After completing the initial phase of the lung nodule detection system, the final outcome consists of the segmented lung tissues, which have been successfully isolated and identified from the input data. In [10] the lung image can be taken from CT medical modalities. Preprocessing technique can be applied to reduce the computational complexity and a filter namely wiener is used to remove the salt and pepper noise [e]. Then the lung image can be smoothed by Gabor filter to decrement the background noise and the image enhancement can be done through power-law transform. Finally, the segmentation can be done by Fuzzy segmentation.

2. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A different method for predicting lung tumor from its images is proposed with the use of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) under different medical modalities is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Lung Tumor Detection System with Deep CNN

The Input image for the work has been chosen as a CT lung image of few patients with and without tumor. For this purpose, few Computed Tomography images are obtained from an hospital for the early tumor detection. Preprocessing techniques is required for performing a better detection. Preprocessing improves the further processing and for getting better classifications. This phase is used to remove all the noises in the scanned CT image. Hence, this step helps in order to improve the visual clarity of the image.

The preprocessed image is fed as input to the convolution layer. Here the image is convolved with a filter of size 3x3. 25 such filters are used and hence different feature

maps have been obtained. Convolved images are given as input to the next layer in deep CNN.

The normalization layer ensures that each input channel across a mini-batch is standardized, resulting in consistent and comparable values, which aids in stabilizing and improving the training process of the neural network. Batch normalization layer in deep CNN does the action of the normalization of the convolved images. Also, batch normalization is done in mini batches. Mini batch is a subset of training set. For a batch normalization to be performed in a mini batch, each pixel of the feature channel is modified using the following equation.

$$\hat{x} = x_i - \mu_m / ((\sigma_m)^2 + \epsilon) \quad (1)$$

Where, \hat{x} is the normalized value, x_i is the input in each mini batch, μ_m is the mini batch mean, σ_m is the mini batch standard deviation and ϵ is the stabilization constant.

Figure 2: Representation of Batch Normalization Process

The pixel values of batch-normalized images are integers based on the assignment of stabilization constant. Stabilization constant is assigned a value 1 when the batch variance σ_m^2 is very small.

Because of the normalization, numerical stability can be maintained and also the performance of the CNN is improved during training. Figure 2 shows the functions performed in batch normalization layer.

The input in each mini batch gives a normalized output \hat{x} based on the mini batch mean μ_m and mini batch variance σ_m^2 .

$$\mu_m = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^r x_i \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_m^2 = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^r (x_i - \mu_m)^2 \quad (3)$$

The mini batch mean and variance are calculated as given in Equation (2) and (3) respectively. The real output of the batch normalization layer is the one obtained by scaling and shifting the normalized values \hat{x} . The learnable parameters τ and δ , scales and shifts the normalized values obtained in a mini batch and produce the output of batch normalization layer as given in Equation (4).

$$y_i = \tau \hat{x}_i + \delta \quad (4)$$

Previous output is fed as input to this rectification layer. The normalization layer, along with its activation function, helps in ensuring that the input data is appropriately scaled and transformed, contributing to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the neural network during training and inference. Activation function decides the final value of a neuron. Consider a scenario where a cell value in a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is intended to be ideally 1, but due to practical limitations, it takes on a value of 0.85, as the maximum achievable probability is never exactly 1. To address this, an activation function is applied to each element, offering a mechanism to modify the values accordingly. For instance, if a cell value exceeds 0.7, it is set to 1; otherwise, it is set to 0. By employing such an activation function, one can obtain an image with sharper features, improving the overall quality and clarity of the CNN's output.

Convolutional networks often integrate local or global pooling layers to optimize the computational efficiency of the model. These pooling layers play a crucial role in reducing the spatial dimensions of the data while preserving the essential features. Local pooling is applied by combining the outputs of small neuron clusters, usually in the form of 2 x 2 regions. On the other hand, global pooling operates on all the neurons within the convolutional layer. Furthermore, pooling operations can either compute the maximum value (max pooling) or the average value (average pooling) of the selected neurons. The pooling process aids in capturing the most relevant information from the input data, making the network more robust and efficient in handling complex tasks such as image recognition and object detection. Average pooling gives the average value from the selected neurons.

Fully connected layers, also known as dense layers, establish direct connections between every neuron in the preceding layer to each neuron in the subsequent layer. This connectivity pattern resembles the architecture of a traditional multi-layer perceptron neural network (MLP). In these layers, each neuron's output is connected as an input to all the neurons in the following layer, enabling comprehensive information flow and complex interactions between the network's components. This arrangement allows the model to learn intricate patterns and relationships within the data, making fully connected layers a fundamental component in deep learning architectures. The flattened fully connected layer classifies the images. Performance is also evaluated by using the formula as given below

$$\text{Accuracy} = (\text{TP} + \text{TN}) / \text{Total sample} \quad (5)$$

Where, TP is True Positive (Correct matching of pixels with correct identification of samples) and TN is True Negative (Correct result but false matching of samples). The Overall accuracy in classification is 94.1178.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Can net, used the Caffe deep learning framework. Within the framework, deep networks can be constructed by carefully selecting suitable layers and defining their connections to preceding and succeeding layers. This flexibility allows for the creation of intricate architectures, which proves especially advantageous in representing CT scan data effectively. By tailoring the network design and layer configurations, the framework empowers researchers and practitioners to design models that can accurately capture complex patterns and features present in CT scans, leading to improved performance in medical image analysis tasks and other relevant applications. The CT scans obtained from a patient encompass a comprehensive dataset consisting of both the imaging data itself and the corresponding labels or annotations associated with each scan. During both the training and testing phases, this label plays a crucial role as it is utilized to facilitate the evaluation, validation, and fine-tuning of the predictive algorithms or models employed in analyzing the CT scans of the patient. When using large batch sizes, the learning process tends to slow down considerably, often taking several days to complete, and may even terminate prematurely due to limited memory resources. To address this issue, we opted for a batch size of 20 in most of our experiments. During the training phase of the network, we ran it for 40 iterations. To ensure a stable and efficient learning process, we set the initial learning rate to 0.01 and decreased it every 40 iterations to fine-tune the model effectively.

In order to assess the performance and measure the effectiveness of the classification process applied to the CT scans, a rigorous calculation of the accuracy is performed, taking into account the concordance between the predicted classes and the ground truth annotations associated with each scan. Despite the Can Net architecture classification achieving a consistent level of accuracy, it falls noticeably short in comparison to our deep convolutional neural network (CNN) model, which consistently demonstrates a significantly higher accuracy rate. With an increase in the number of iterations, the Can Net model exhibits a noticeable improvement in accuracy, showing a progressive enhancement over time. When compared to a traditional artificial neural network (ANN), the Can Net model demonstrates a remarkable 65% improvement in accuracy, showcasing its superior performance and efficacy in classification tasks. Also experiment has been done in deep learning with 8 layered deep CNN. The SDGM training model with epoch 40 and learning rate of 0.01 is investigated.

Investigation with sample input images are shown in Figure 3. Also, Figure 4 shows the training accuracy and loss. It shows that good accuracy and zero loss after 30 iterations. Such trained model gave a good accuracy in classification of cancer or non-cancer from the CT image. Accuracy obtained is 98.1%

Figure 3: Experiment showing few Sample Input Images

Figure 4: Experiment Showing Accuracy and Loss

4. PERFORMANCE OF INVESTIGATED METHODS

Investigation done in different methods such as ANN, Can Net and CNN with 8 layers is compared with respect to their accuracy. The accuracy varies between the methods. Below chart shows the accuracy obtained in each method.

Figure 5: Accuracy in Classification of Lung Tumor in Various Investigation Methods

Among the 3 methods investigated the accuracy in classification is best while using deep CNN as the architecture. ANN and CAN NET shows around 9% and 44% less accuracy respectively when compared to deep CNN.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

A solution to efficiently classify lung cancer screening thoracic CT scans is achieved by leveraging the power of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which are effectively employed to accurately and effectively classify the scans. By utilizing CNNs, the laborious task of manually extracting features for classification is significantly mitigated, eliminating the need for specialized domain knowledge.

Deep CNNs excel at automatically learning and extracting relevant features directly from the raw input data, allowing for a more streamlined and efficient classification process. This eliminates the time-consuming and error-prone process of handcrafting features, making the classification of lung cancer screening thoracic CT scans more accessible and less dependent on expert knowledge in the specific domain. The documented classification accuracy indicates that Can Net is 65% more than other classification method. Also deep classification gave better results. To further explore the potential for increasing accuracy, it is possible to conduct additional experimentation by modifying various hyper parameters of the CNN. By systematically adjusting parameters such as learning rate, batch size, network depth, or activation functions, it becomes feasible to fine-tune the CNN model and optimize its performance for classifying lung cancer screening thoracic CT scans. Through this iterative process of hyper parameter tuning, the accuracy of the CNN can be enhanced, ultimately improving the effectiveness of the classification task.

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